

Comparison analysis of color, bw and old-filter images with commercial and open source Computer Vision tools

José Luis Preza Díaz

jl@preza.org

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I was thinking about this: Are there any differences in computer vision results if i process the same image in full color, black and white and old type filter?

I have done comparisons already between systems, but mainly color images ¹

So i did a test. I chose a simple image off the web of a bowl of fruits in full color (bananas, oranges, apple), i created an image of it in black and white and also one with an „old style photo“ filter. I processed this images with the following computer vision solutions: clarifai food model, google vision, google image search, microsoft azure vision and Yolo v3. All online commercial software is the latest version as of December 26th, 2020

Source images

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACIT49673.2020.9208943> Approach between Different Computer Vision Tools, including Commercial and Open-source, for Improving Cultural Image Access and Analysis. Doi 10.1109/ACIT49673.2020.9208943

Results

Google Image Search

The results for the color picture include bowls of different fruits, not necessarily the ones depicted in the picture being searched

For the black and white and old-style filter, the search focuses on the bowl

Color picture results

The screenshot shows a Google search interface with the query "simple bowl of fruit". The search results include a main image of a fruit bowl, a grid of "Optisch ähnliche Bilder" (visually similar images), and a search result from "mnpriaireroots.com" titled "Art, creation 16 fruit in bowl | Minnesota Prairie Roots".

Google simple bowl of fruit

Alle Bilder Maps Shopping Mehr Einstellungen Suchfilter

Ungefähr 205 Ergebnisse (0,69 Sekunden)

 Bildgröße: 1752 x 1168
Dieses Bild in einer anderen Größe suchen:
Alle Größen - Mittel - Groß

Mögliche verwandte Suchanfrage: [simple bowl of fruit](#)

Optisch ähnliche Bilder

Unangemessene Bilder melden

Seiten mit übereinstimmenden Bildern

mnpriaireroots.com · 2016/02/08 · Diese Seite übersetzen

[Art, creation 16 fruit in bowl | Minnesota Prairie Roots](#)

 848 x 565 · 08.02.2016 — A simple bowl of fruit rests as a work of art and an example of God's Creation.

Black and white picture results

Google serveware

Alle Bilder Maps Shopping Mehr Suche Suchfilter

Ungefähr 4 Ergebnisse (0,56 Sekunden)

 Bildgröße: 1752 x 1168
Keine anderen Größen für dieses Bild gefunden.

Mögliche verwandte Suchanfrage: [serveware](#)

www.crateandbarrel.com > Tabletop & Bar

Serveware & Serving Dish Sets | Crate and Barrel
Entertain your guests in style with serveware sets from Crate and Barrel. Browse glass, metal, ceramic and silver serving dishes for any occasion. Order online.

Optisch ähnliche Bilder

Unangemessene Bilder melden

Old-style filter results

Google serveware

Alle Bilder Maps Shopping Mehr Einstellungen Suchfilter

Ungefähr 1 Ergebnisse (0,90 Sekunden)

 Bildgröße: 1752 x 1168
Keine anderen Größen für dieses Bild gefunden.

Mögliche verwandte Suchanfrage: [serveware](#)

www.crateandbarrel.com > Tabletop & Bar

Serveware & Serving Dish Sets | Crate and Barrel
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Optisch ähnliche Bilder

Unangemessene Bilder melden

Yolo v3

Yolo recognized Bowl, Banana, Apple, Orange for the full color picture. The Black and white returned Banana and Bowl. The old-style filter returned only Bowl.

Google Vision

Google Vision recognized the objects Banana, Apple, Orange (2), food and tableware for the full color picture.

The Black and white returned Banana, Bowl, 3 times fruit and food. The old-style filter returned package goods and food.

Clarifai Food Model

Color picture results include apple, orange, sweet, lemon, citrus, banana, juice, cake, grapefruit, peach, cream, blood orange, mango

Black and white results include coffee, tea, milk, cream, sweet, candy, coconut, espresso, cake,, chocolate, egg, apple, mocha, mochi

Old-style filter results include milk, sweet, coffee, egg, cream,, tea, dairy products ,candy, egg yolk, cake, mochi, pudding, flour

Azure Vision

Azure Vision recognized the Objects Banana (2), Fruit, Orange (2) and Bowl for the full color picture. The Tags sections includes bowl, orange, oranges, apple, and many other results like vegetable, squash, plant, pumkin, etc (38 in total). The Description section includes bowl, indoor, oranges, sitting, table, plant, fruit, filled, green, full, wooden, orange, basket, plate, blue, cut. As caption it generates: "a bowl of oranges on a table".

The Black and white returned as Objects: Banana, Bowl, Orange, one orange and the apple are recognized as fruit. The Tags section includes: bowl, indoor, black and white, fruit, plant, apple, food, monochrome, still life photography. The Description section includes: bowl, indoor, sitting, plant, table, banana, fruit, wooden, filled, full, food, close, apple, green, large, kitchen, oranges. As caption it generates: „a close up of a bowl of fruit“

The old-style filter returned no Objects section, in the Tags section includes Bowl, eggs, food, dairy, orange, dessert. In the Description section includes cup, bowl, food, indoor, sitting, table, orange, fruit, plate, filled, oranges, close, banana, wooden, cake, cut,cream. As caption it generates: "a close up of a bowl".

Conclusion

It seems that most systems work better with color pictures. The reason for this might be that those systems have been trained mostly with color pictures. To improve results for black and white and other filtered images, the systems will need to be trained not only with full color images but also with images (including the same color images) in black and white and other needed filters.

References

Yolo v3 with Keras <https://github.com/qqwweee/keras-yolo3>

Clarifai www.clarifai.com

Microsoft Azure Vision <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/cognitive-services/computer-vision/>

Google Vision <https://cloud.google.com/vision/>